

HIGH TEMPERATURE TENSILE STRENGTH ANALYSIS OF C/SiC COMPOSITE AND SUPERALLOY BOLTED JOINT STRUCTURE

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Keywords: Ceramic matrix composite, Progressive damage analysis, Tensile performance, Bolted joints, Finite element analysis

ABSTRACT

Ceramic Composite Materials (CMC) and superalloy bolted joint structures have received considerable attention for propulsion system and vehicle hot structure applications. In their service conditions, the hybrid bolted joint structures are subjected to superimposed thermal and mechanical loads. The thermal expansion mismatch between CMC and superalloy plates will cause complex thermal stress and strain distribution at hole-edge area and significant changes in assembly parameters of the joint. These effects might lead to early damage of joint structure, which will endanger the structural integrity and load carrying capacity of aircraft components. To address this issue, in this work, a progressive damage model for 2D woven C/SiC composite including a nonlinear macroscopic constituent model and Tsai-Wu failure criterion was established to predict high temperature tensile performance and failure behavior of single-lap, single-bolt 2D C/SiC composite and superalloy joint. The variations of failure strength with imposed temperature and bolt preload were discussed for the studied bolted joint. The present work provides valuable information in design of CMC joint structures on next-generation aircrafts.

1 INTRODUCTION

C/SiC ceramic matrix composites have been widely used for hot structures in aerospace engineering, due to their obvious advantages in high temperature resistance, high specific strength and stiffness, low thermal expansion coefficient, and excellent oxidation resistance. To achieve successful applications at elevated temperature, the ceramic matrix composites are inevitably connected with metal alloy components [1-4]. Among the existing joint methods, bolted joint has attracted considerable attention because of its high load transfer capability, easy assemble and disassemble, and excellent environmental damages tolerance. In their services, the CMC and superalloy bolted joint structures are subjected to superimposed thermal and mechanical loads. The thermal expansion mismatch between CMC and superalloy plates will cause complex thermal stress and strain distribution at hole-edge area and significant changes in assembly parameters of the joint. These effects might lead to early damage of joint structure, which will endanger the structural integrity and load carrying capacity of aircraft components. In previous studies, great effort has been devoted to investigate their mechanical performance by experimental and numerical methods [5-14]. In contrast to the carbon-fiber/polymer composite counterparts, research on failure behaviors of CMC joint structures was relatively limited [15-18]. Mei et al. [16] experimentally investigated the tensile properties and oxidation behavior of 2D C/SiC bolts prepared by chemical vapor infiltration in a simulated re-entry environment. The results showed that all the tensile strengths of 2D C/SiC bolts at test temperatures of 1300°C, 1600°C and 1800°C decreased, respectively, retaining 85%, 92%, and 94% of the virgin properties at room temperature. The tensile strengths and times to failure of 2D C/SiC bolts slightly increased with increase of test temperature from 1300°C to 1800°C. Li et al. [17] studied the damage mode and fracture load of C/SiC joints via a comparison of the results of simulations and experiments. The maximum stress failure criterion was used to determine the damage of the C/SiC composites in simulations. The influences of hole parameters including ratios of edge distance to diameter, width to diameter and hole distance to diameter, on the mechanical properties of C/SiC joints with pins or bolts were studied. Moreover, Zhao et al. [18] performed failure analyses of

open-hole C/SiC composite laminates with different failure criteria and material degradation models, among which the most suitable combination was filtered by comparing the numerical results with existing experimental data. Furthermore, the failure process of a three-bolt C/SiC composite joint was predicted using the proposed progressive failure model. However, little attention was paid on the high temperature tensile behavior of CMC bolted joints. To address the above deficiencies in open literatures, a 3D finite element analysis coupled with a non-linear progressive damage model is firstly carried out to predict tensile performance and failure behavior of single-lap, single-bolt hybrid CMC/superalloy joint. The variations of strength and the associated damage mechanisms with temperature rise will be discussed for the studied hybrid bolted joint.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

2D plain-woven C/SiC composite to GH4169 superalloy, single-bolt, single-lap joint structure will be used for this study, and the geometry and dimensions of the joint are shown in Figure 1. Both the C/SiC composite plate and GH4169 alloy plate are 120 mm long, with 30 mm gripping length. The thicknesses of the CMC plate and GH4169 alloy plate are 3.0 mm and 2.0 mm, respectively. The two plates are assembled together using a 6.0 mm diameter bolt made of GH4141 alloy. The 2D woven C/SiC composite is assumed as transversal isotropic material and the constituent model exhibits non-linear behavior under uniaxial tension and shear loads. Due to higher yield strength of high temperature alloy than that of CMC, the failure process of the bolted joint is dominated by the composite plate. Therefore, only elastic behavior was considered in this analysis for the superalloy plate and bolt. The assigned mechanical properties of GH4169 and GH4141 alloy from China Aviation Materials Handbook [19] are listed in Table 1. Finite element model was established to simulate quasi-statically tensile process of the hybrid C/SiC composite-superalloy bolted joint via Abaqus/standard software. Three-dimensional eight-node reduced-integration C3D8R elements with hourglass control were used to discretize the composite laminates, superalloy plate and mechanical fastener. Five contact pairs for the joint structure were defined between fastener shank and holes of plates, fastener head or nut and the outer surfaces of the two plates, and the faying surface of two plates. A finite sliding contact formulation that allows for arbitrary relative displacement and rotation between contacting bodies was adopted between all contact interfaces in the model. A classic Coulomb friction was assigned to all contacted surfaces with a friction coefficient of 0.3. The bolt-hole fit condition can be changed through setting Interference fit values of the contact pairs between fastener shank and holes in two plates. The preload produced by the assembly tightening torque was applied through Bolt load function in ABAQUS. The hybrid joint structure was applied a given uniform temperature load. The right end of superalloy plate was held fixed in all three translational directions (U_x , U_y and U_z). The left end of the composite plate was declared as a rigid body and had tie relationship with a reference node. Thus, the motion of the right side surface was governed by the motion of the reference node, which was held fixed in two translational directions (U_y and U_z) and three rotational directions (R_x , R_y and R_z), while prescribed loads were quasi-statically applied along U_x direction. A plot of finite element model for the hybrid CMC-superalloy single-bolt, single-lap joint is illustrated in Figure 2, in which details such as boundary conditions and set contact pairs are included.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry configuration of the CMC/superalloy bolted joint (all dimensions in mm)

Property	GH4169	GH4141
Young's moduli (GPa)	204	221
Poisson's ratio	0.3	0.3
Yield stress (MPa)	1040	1070

Table 1: Mechanical properties of GH 4169 alloy plate and GH4141 bolt

Figure 2: Finite element model and set contact pairs of 2D C/SiC composite-superalloy bolted joint structure

3 PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE ANALYSIS METHOD

3.1 Constituent model for 2D C/SiC composite

Based on extensive testing observations by researchers, it has been found that C/SiC composites exhibit non-linearity and pseudo-plasticity under uniaxial tensile and shear loading [19]. For current analysis, a macroscopic constituent model proposed by Li et al. [20] is adopted here to characterize the mechanical behavior of 2D plain-woven C/SiC composite materials. This constituent model is not only capable of describing the nonlinear damage behavior and pseudo-plasticity of C/SiC composite, but also capable of taking into account unilateral effect and damage-deactivation in tension and compression processes for the material. By their model, the experimentally measured stress-strain relationships under uniaxial tensile and shear loading for the material are fitted with five-order polynomial functions, as shown below:

$$\sigma_i = A_1 \varepsilon_i + A_2 \varepsilon_i^2 + A_3 \varepsilon_i^3 + A_4 \varepsilon_i^4 + A_5 \varepsilon_i^5 \quad (0 \leq \varepsilon_i \leq \varepsilon_i^f, i = 1, 2) \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_{12} = B_1 \gamma_{12} + B_2 \gamma_{12}^2 + B_3 \gamma_{12}^3 + B_4 \gamma_{12}^4 + B_5 \gamma_{12}^5 \quad (|\gamma_{12}| \leq \gamma_{12}^f) \quad (2)$$

Where ε_i^f is the tensile fracture strain in principle direction 1 and 2, respectively. γ_{12}^f is the shear fracture strain in the 1-2 plane. A_j and B_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) are the fitted coefficients.

Then, the tangent modulus at various strain levels used for damage analysis is obtained through derivation to the detectable strain according to the fitted stress-strain relationship.

$$E_i^{tan} = \frac{d\sigma_i}{d\varepsilon_i} = A_1 + 2A_2 \varepsilon_i + 3A_3 \varepsilon_i^2 + 4A_4 \varepsilon_i^3 + 5A_5 \varepsilon_i^4 \quad (0 \leq \varepsilon_i \leq \varepsilon_i^f, i = 1, 2) \quad (3)$$

$$G_{12}^{tan} = \frac{d\tau_{12}}{d\gamma_{12}} = B_1 + 2B_2 \gamma_{12} + 3B_3 \gamma_{12}^2 + 4B_4 \gamma_{12}^3 + 5B_5 \gamma_{12}^4 \quad (|\gamma_{12}| \leq \gamma_{12}^f) \quad (4)$$

From the above formulas, when the tensile strain ε_i and shear strain γ_{12} equal zero, the E_i^{tan} and G_{12}^{tan} are the initial elastic and shear modulus of the C/SiC composite. Figure 3 shows the measured stress-strain curves under uniaxial tension and shear loading for a 2D plain-woven C/SiC

composite material provided by material suppliers and the fitted results. The mechanical properties of the composite material used for analysis are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 3: The measured stress-stain curves provided by material suppliers and the fitted results for a 2D plain-woven C/SiC composite plate under uniaxial tension (a) and shear (b) loading

Property	Symbol	Value
Initial elastic modulus (GPa)	$E_{11}=E_{22}$	114.13
	E_{33}	88.90
Initial shear modulus (GPa)	G_{12}	45.12
	$G_{13}=G_{23}$	25.63
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.13
	$\nu_{13}=\nu_{23}$	0.26
Tensile strength (MPa)	$X_t=Y_t$	156
	Z_t	350
Compressive strength (MPa)	$X_c=Y_c$	350
	Z_c	420
In-plane shear strength (MPa)	$S_{12}=S_{13}=S_{23}$	83

Table 2: Mechanical properties of 2D plain-woven C/SiC composite material

3.2 Damage analysis procedure

To implement a non-linear progressive failure analysis of hybrid C/SiC composite and superalloy bolted joint structure, a user-defined subroutine UMAT including the aforementioned constitutive model, failure criterion and material degradation rule was embedded into the general package ABAQUS®. The proposed analysis method starts with the generation of finite element model for the studied bolted joint by using the material properties, geometrical parameters, boundary conditions, initial load and load step as inputs. Then, a non-linear stress analysis is carried out to calculate the stress at each element on the bolted joint using the above-described constituent models. Tsai-Wu strength criterion [21] is used for evaluation of failure occurrence on basis of the calculated structural stresses. If the failure criterion is violated, the applied load is increased by a load increment and the stiffness parameters for CMC are updated in accordance with the obtained stress levels. Otherwise, the material stiffness parameters are reduced to 1% of its undamaged value for the C/SiC composite. The simulation stops until the final failure of the composite structure is detected.

4 MODEL VALIDATION AND PARAMETRIC STUDIES

4.1 Progressive damage model validation

To validate the proposed damage analysis method for the 2D woven C/SiC composite materials, a tensile process of an open-hole laminate was simulated for lack of data on hybrid C/SiC composite and superalloy bolted joint in open publications. The geometric configuration, mechanical properties and measured stress-strain curves of the 2D woven C/SiC composite for this validation were given in the literature [20]. The uniaxial tensile process for the open-hole composite plate was simulated by using the commercial FEA software ABAQUS, and the predicted tensile stress-strain relationship are shown in Figure 4. The comparison of the simulated and experimental results [20] showed that the predicted strength of 135.5 MPa using the developed method is in good agreement with the experimental value of 150 MPa, with a relative error of 9.6%, which validates the effectiveness of the proposed progressive failure model in this paper. A relative error of no more than 10% is acceptable in engineering applications, considering that various factors can result in errors between the measured and predicted results, such as the scattering of experimental results caused by various levels of intrinsic defects in fabrication of composites, simplifications in finite element model, and the selected failure criterion and degradation rule in the progressive damage simulation.

Figure 4: Comparison of simulated tensile stress and strain relationship with experimental results in Li et al. [20] for 2D woven C/SiC composite open-hole plate

4.2 High temperature tensile behavior of the studied hybrid bolted joint

To observe the high temperature performance of the CMC and superalloy bolted joint, the uniaxial tensile processes of the joints are simulated as they are subjected to room temperature (25°C), 150 °C, 300 °C, 150 °C, 600 °C, 750 °C temperature loads, respectively. Bolt preload of 6000 N is applied to all the studied joint structures. To avoid the occurrence of interference caused by thermal expansion mismatch between the fastener shank and holes on plates when the joints are heated to high temperatures, 0.7% bolt-hole clearance is imposed to the fasteners. The simulated load-displacement curves of the hybrid bolted joints under different temperatures and the variations of the failure strength with temperatures are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. As it can be seen, the failure load decreases first from 2886 N at 25°C to 2695 N at 300°C, and then increases to 2815 N at 600 °C, and finally declines to 2523 N at 750°C as the applied temperature rises from 25°C to 750°C. The varying trend of structural strength with temperature can be reduced to the following reasons. On the one hand, when the temperature increases, the large difference in thermal expansion coefficient between the ceramic matrix composite material and the high-temperature alloy leads to the pretension force relaxation of the bolted joint, which will reduce the load bearing capacity of the structure. On the other hand, the high temperature also leads to the clearance between the fastener shank and hole on

composite plate smaller, and thus makes the bearing capacity of the structure rise. The superposition of these factors makes the structural strength exhibit complex trend with temperature.

Figure 5: The simulated load-displacement curves of the hybrid bolted joints under different temperatures

Figure 6: Variations of the failure strength with temperature of the hybrid bolted joints

With the 0.7% bolt hole clearance, the simulated load-displacement responses at 750 °C of the joints with different levels of bolt preload are shown in Figure 7. The variations of failure strength with bolt preload are shown in Figure 8. As it can be seen, the application of bolt preload leads to minor influence on the stiffness of the joint structure. However, the failure strength exhibits upward trend with the increase of bolt preload, and the value increases from 2439 N for 5.5 kN preload to 2773 N for 7.3 kN preload, accounting for 13.7% increase in failure strength.

Figure 7: The simulated load-displacement curves at 750°C of the hybrid bolted joints with different levels of preload

Figure 8: Variations of the failure strength at 750°C with bolt preload of the hybrid bolted joints

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, a progressive damage model was established to predict tensile performance and associated failure behavior of single-lap, single-bolt 2D C/SiC composite and superalloy joint. A macroscopic constituent model was adopted to describe the nonlinear damage behavior, as well as the unilateral effect and damage-deactivation in tension and compression processes of C/SiC composite. The progressive failure analysis for the hybrid bolted joint was implemented by using a user-defined subroutine UMAT embedded into the general package ABAQUS. On basis of the developed damage model, a parametric study was carried out to illustrate the effects of temperature and bolt preload on mechanical behaviors for the hybrid bolted joint. It was found that the failure load decreases first from 2886 N at 25°C to 2695 N at 300°C, and then increases to 2815 N at 600 °C, and finally declines to 2523 N at 750°C as the applied temperature rises from 25°C to 750°C. The application of bolt preload leads to minor influence on the stiffness of the joint structure. However, the failure strength exhibits upward trend with the increase of bolt preload, and the value increases from 2439 N for 5.5 kN preload to 2773 N for 7.3 kN preload, accounting for 13.7% increase in failure strength. The present work provides valuable information in design of joint structure and promoting extensive application of ceramic matrix composites in next-generation aircrafts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Pre-Research Foundation of Shenyang Aircraft Design and Research Institute, Aviation Industry Corporation of China (Grant No. JH20128255).

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